

EVIDENCE-BASED TOXICOLOGY
An open science journal for environmental health research

Evaluation Report (peer-review round 3) for **TEBT-2023-0010**

Submission Information Table

Submission Title	Evidence on the effects of Flame Retardant substances at ecologically relevant endpoints: A Systematic Map Protocol
Submission Reference	TEBT-2023-0010
Handling Editor	Paul Whaley, ORCID 0000-0003-4021-0785
Number of Reviewers	2
Submission Type	Secondary Study Protocol ▾
Preprint DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10617509
Status	Accepted ▾
Evaluation Date	27 Jun 2024
Evaluation Round	Peer-review round 3
Recommendation	Accept ▾
Handling Editor's Explanation for Recommendation	Revision recommendations after round 2 of peer-review were minor. The handling editor is confident that the authors have responded satisfactorily to the reviewer comments and no further rounds of peer-review are necessary.

Acceptance Note

Written by the Handling Editor as a summary of the key points from the peer-review process

This manuscript has been accepted for publication by the handling editor after assessment in 1 round of editorial triage and 2 rounds of peer-review. The evaluators found the protocol to be a thoughtful and well-planned approach to conducting an evidence mapping exercise that should be of value to the research community.

During triage, the handling editor requested that a dummy dataset be provided to allow the planned database to be evaluated by the editor and peer-reviewers. During peer-review, the evaluators identified issues relating to the comprehensiveness and reproducibility of the authors' search strategy, to some aspects of the transparency of the coding strategy, and to how the coding decisions by the authors were to be quality controlled. There were also questions about the feasibility of the project, given the scale of the planned work in relation to the size of the research team.

The authors addressed these issues by bringing an information scientist into the author team, by further developing and refining their coding strategy, and by making clear that their approach to quality control relates to identifying error rates in coding rather than aiming to eliminate errors altogether.

The following points of scientific interest were surfaced by the review process:

1. While the authors' approach to quality control will not minimise coding errors in the way that full duplicate data abstraction would achieve, a transparent accounting of error rate allows full interpretation of potential limitations of the coding strategy. The evaluators felt this is appropriate for balancing the breadth of the planned database with the resources available to the researchers.
2. There was some disagreement among the evaluators as to whether an evidence map should include interactive visualisations. This was settled by EBT submission policy. This policy makes it optional for evidence maps to include interactive visualisations, but requires that such maps include data files that can be relatively easily converted into visualisations and otherwise developed or extended by their users.

A complete record of the evaluation reports for this submission can be found at DOI [10.5281/zenodo.10302107](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10302107).